

COLLEGE GRADUATES' EMPLOYABILITY AND BILINGUALISM RELATIONSHIP AT THE LOWER RGV BORDER, USA-MEXICO.

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Abstract: *This study explores the impact of enrolling in bilingual college courses on students' employability in the business sector of the Rio Grande Valley (RGV) border region between the USA and Mexico. The hypothesis is that structured bilingual education at college can enhance students' career readiness and competitiveness in bilingual business environments. The surveyed subjects are students enrolled in business-related courses, and the research focus was on the students' bilingual proficiency (English and Spanish). The research highlights that formal bilingual training plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between domestic conversational bilingualism and professional bilingual competency. The findings provide valuable insights for college authorities and human resources professionals, emphasizing the importance of coordinating and developing strategies to align supply and demand regarding bilingual proficiency in the professionals' labor force at the RGV border region.*

Keywords: *Bilingualism, Border Region, Higher Education Bilingual Curriculum, Employment, Business Professionals.*

1. Introduction

The Rio Grande Valley (RGV) is a bilingual region where Spanish and English coexist, often blending through code-switching and Spanglish (Poplack, 1980). While this bilingualism fosters communication and social mobility, many University of Texas Rio Grande Valley (UTRGV) students struggle to use formal Spanish in professional contexts,

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which limits their job readiness in the business sector. This study examines whether structured bilingual education at the college level can bridge the gap between informal and professional bilingualism and strengthen students' employability. This approach responds to the growing demand for professionals equipped with the language skills necessary to perform effectively in bilingual work environments.

2. Literature Review

Follow the instructions for formatting: Bilingualism in the RGV often extends across fourth and fifth generations, reflecting a strong cultural and linguistic presence in the region (Anderson-Mejías, 2005). While U.S. bilingual education policy has fluctuated, heritage-language and immersion programs continue to gain recognition and support (Moses, 2000; Lenker & Rhodes, 2007).

UTRGV's Office of Bilingual Integration, through the B3 Initiative, promotes bilingual, bicultural, and biliterate development by offering designated bilingual courses. Scholars emphasize the importance of bilingual communication and cultural adaptability for global competence and career readiness (Grosjean, 2010; Lakshman et al., 2021; Herrera & Radosavljević, 2023).

Building on this foundation, the present study examines whether structured bilingual coursework helps bridge the gap between informal language use and professional application among UTRGV business students in the RGV, as emphasized by prior research on the importance of academic bilingual development and workplace communication (Grosjean, 2010; Herrera & Radosavljević, 2023).

3. Design of Study

This research study is best classified as a mixed-methods, cross-sectional, exploratory study with quasi-experimental elements. It is mixed-methods because it integrates both quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of bilingual readiness and perceptions. The cross-sectional nature of the study refers to its data collection at a single point in time, offering a snapshot of students' attitudes and competencies during one academic semester. It is exploratory because it seeks to investigate a relatively under-researched area—student readiness for structured bilingual coursework—without testing a narrowly defined theory. Lastly, it includes quasi-experimental elements due to the presence of two naturally occurring student groups (English-only vs. bilingual sections), enabling comparison without random assignment.

3.1 Objective

This study explores UTRGV students' readiness to engage in structured bilingual coursework in business-related fields, with a focus on their proficiency in English and Spanish. It also examines the relevance of professional Spanish in workplace contexts and its relationship to job readiness in the RGV business sector.

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3.2 Hypothesis

Structured bilingual education at the college level has the potential to significantly improve students' career readiness and increase their competitiveness in bilingual business environments, particularly in regions like the RGV where bilingual proficiency is a key asset in the labor market. Materials and Methods

3.3 Participants

The study involved 101 students enrolled in two sections of the MGMT-3361 course at UTRGV during the Fall 2024 semester. One section was delivered in English, and the other followed a bilingual English–Spanish format.

3.4 Procedure

A survey approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) was administered electronically to ensure participant anonymity. The instrument gathered both quantitative and qualitative data related to students' bilingual proficiency and their perceptions of bilingualism in professional contexts.

3.5 Instrument and Focus Areas

Although the complete survey consisted of 60 items across six sections, only 24 items were analyzed for the purposes of this study. These items were selected based on their relevance to assessing students' readiness for bilingual education in business and were grouped into the following focus areas:

- Demographics: Country of birth, primary household language, and dual nationality.
- Language Proficiency: Self-assessed skills in speaking, reading, and writing in both English and Spanish.
- Bicultural Identity: Degree of identification with a bicultural background and the perceived value of bilingualism, biculturalism, and biliteracy.
- Work Experience: Previous paid work experience and current employment status.
- Spanish Language Use in the Workplace: Extent and context of Spanish use in professional or job-related settings.

4. Results

4.1 Demographics

The survey included 101 students enrolled in MGMT-3361 courses. Most participants (98%) identified as Hispanic. Regarding place of birth, 87% were born in the United States and 13% in Mexico. A total of 60% reported holding dual nationality.

Concerning household primary language(s), 73 students (72%) reported Spanish, and 39 students (39%) reported English as languages spoken at home. Since participants

were allowed to select more than one option, the total exceeds 100%. Specifically, 12 students (11%) indicated that both English and Spanish are spoken in their households. These results confirm that most students live in predominantly Spanish-speaking or bilingual households, reflecting the region's multicultural and multilingual environment.

4.2 Language Proficiency

4.2.1 Speaking Skills

In English, 57 students identified as native speakers, representing 56.4%. Additionally, 37 students reported being proficient non-native speakers, which corresponds to 36.6%.

In Spanish, 50 students identified as native speakers, accounting for 49.5%, and 23 students were proficient non-native speakers, representing 22.8%.

Furthermore, 6 students were native speakers of both English and Spanish, which equals 5.9%. Another 60 students were proficient in both languages, totaling 59.4%. In total, 66 students were either native or proficient speakers of both English and Spanish, which represents 65.3% of the participants.

4.2.2 Reading Skills

For English, 93 students reported a high level of reading proficiency, representing 92.1%. An additional 7 students reported intermediate-level reading skills, equivalent to 6.9%.

For Spanish, 57 students reported a high level of reading proficiency, which accounts for 57.6%. Seventeen students reported intermediate reading skills, representing 17.2%.

4.2.3 Writing Skills

In English, 91 students reported a high level of writing proficiency (80–100%), which represents 90.1%. An additional 10 students indicated an intermediate level (60–79%), accounting for 9.9%.

In Spanish, 44 students reported a high level of writing proficiency, representing 44.4%. Another 22 students demonstrated an intermediate level, which corresponds to 22.2%. In a separate item regarding the B3 model (Bilingualism, Biculturalism, and Biliteracy), 92% of students affirmed that they value all three components.

4.3 Bicultural Identity

As part of the survey, students were asked to describe their cultural background and indicate whether they consider themselves bicultural. A total of 87% of participants identified as bicultural individuals. The majority described themselves as Mexican American, the most frequently reported identity. Other backgrounds mentioned in open-ended responses included Mexican-American-Cuban, Guatemalan-American, Mexican-

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American-Italian, and Mexican-Canadian-Taiwanese heritage. These results reflect the cultural diversity represented among students.

In a separate item regarding the B3 model (Bilingualism, Biculturalism, and Biliteracy), 92% of students affirmed that they value all three components.

These results highlight a strong sense of cultural self-identification among participants and reflect the diverse linguistic and cultural perspectives within the student population.

4.4 Work Experience

To better understand participants' professional backgrounds, students were asked about their employment status. A total of 83% reported having previous paid work experience, and 71% were employed at the time of the survey. These results indicate that most students were actively engaged in the workforce or had recent experience in professional settings. This provides context for analyzing how language skills are used in real job environments.

4.5 Spanish Language Use in the Workplace

Students were also asked to report how they used Spanish in their current or past employment settings. A total of 61% indicated that they used Spanish informally with colleagues or clients, while 54% used it for formal, job-related communication. Additionally, 16% reported that being fluent in Spanish was required for their hiring, and another 16% stated they did not use Spanish at all in their workplace.

These results indicate that Spanish is used in a wide range of workplace situations, including both casual and formal interactions. Its presence in the professional environment reflects students' everyday bilingual demands, particularly in regions like the Rio Grande Valley.

5. Discussion

5.1 Bilingual Engagement and Professional Readiness

The results of this study reveal strong bilingual competencies among UTRGV students. These competencies are evident in their language proficiency, cultural identity, and the use of Spanish in professional environments. The four main indicators examined in this study, which include demographics, language proficiency, bicultural identity, and workplace language use, show that students consistently engage with both English and Spanish in academic and professional settings.

A total of 55 students (61%) reported using Spanish informally with colleagues or clients in their workplace. In addition, 49 students (54%) indicated that they use Spanish for formal, job-related communication. However, only 14 students (16%) stated that fluency in Spanish was a requirement for hiring, and 14 students (16%) reported not using Spanish at all in their workplace. These results suggest that while Spanish is not always a formal job requirement, it plays an important role in daily work interactions.

Regarding cultural identity, 88 students (87%) identified as bicultural, and 93 students (92%) expressed that they value bilingualism, biculturalism, and biliteracy. These findings show that students not only possess strong language skills but also recognize the importance of their cultural background. Their profiles align closely with the linguistic and cultural dynamics of the Rio Grande Valley.

Given these results, there is a clear opportunity to enhance students' academic and professional preparation through structured bilingual coursework. Such courses can strengthen their ability to use Spanish in formal business contexts, moving beyond informal usage. This type of academic support is particularly relevant in the Rio Grande Valley, where bilingualism is both a social reality and a professional advantage.

In this context, bilingual readiness supports the development of university-level bilingual education. In turn, this contributes to expanding employment opportunities for students in the business sector of the region.

6. Conclusions

The findings support the hypothesis that UTRGV students possess the competencies to benefit from structured bilingual education. Across all focus areas, students demonstrated strong bilingual and bicultural engagement, particularly in their language proficiency and use of Spanish in professional contexts.

However, a gap remains between informal bilingualism and the formal language skills required in business and professional settings. This reinforces the importance of offering bilingual coursework that strengthens students' ability to communicate effectively in academic and workplace environments.

A total of 93 students (92%) expressed that they value bilingualism, biculturalism, and biliteracy, which are the three components measured under the B3 indicator. This result reflects not only cultural identity but also alignment with institutional initiatives such as UTRGV's B3 program.

Expanding structured bilingual education would improve students' readiness for the regional labor market and enhance their employability in multicultural business environments. It is both a culturally responsive and strategic approach that positions UTRGV to lead in preparing a bilingual workforce for the Rio Grande Valley.

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ZAPOŠLJIVOST I ODNOS DVOJEZIČNOSTI DIPLOMIRANIH STUDENATA NA DONJOJ RGV GRANICI, SAD-MEKSIKO.

Rezime: Ova studija istražuje utjecaj upisa na dvojezične fakultetske tečajeve na zapošljivost studenata u poslovnom sektoru pogranične regije doline Rio Grande (RGV) između SAD-a i Meksika. Hipoteza je da strukturirano dvojezično obrazovanje na fakultetu može poboljšati spremnost studenata za karijeru i konkurentnost u dvojezičnim poslovnim okruženjima. Ispitanici su studenti upisani na poslovne tečajeve, a fokus istraživanja bio je na dvojezičnom znanju studenata (engleski i španjolski). Istraživanje ističe da formalno dvojezično obrazovanje igra ključnu ulogu u premošćivanju jaza između domaćeg konverzijskog dvojezičnog jezika i profesionalne dvojezične kompetencije. Nalazi pružaju vrijedne uvide sveučilišnim vlastima i stručnjacima za ljudske resurse, naglašavajući važnost koordinacije i razvoja strategija za usklađivanje ponude i potražnje u pogledu dvojezičnog znanja u radnoj snazi stručnjaka u pograničnoj regiji doline Rio Grande (RGV).

Ključne reči: Dvojezičnost, pogranična regija, dvojezični kurikulum visokog obrazovanja, zapošljavanje, poslovni stručnjaci.